

BIOMATERIALS;

Bio-ceramics is a new range of Biomaterial in the field of Biomedical Engineering

K. ASWINI,

Students, Biomedical Engineering

Rajiv Gandhi College of Engineering and Technology,
Puducherry.

INTRODUCTION

During the past 50 years, advances in many specialty bioceramics such as alumina, zirconia, hydroxyapatite, tricalcium phosphates and bioactive glasses have made significant contribution to the development of modern health care industry and have improved the quality of human life. These are the ceramics, which can be used inside the body without rejection to augment or replace various diseased or damaged parts of the musculoskeletal system. They are primarily used as bone substitutes in the biomedical industry due to their biocompatibility, low density, chemical stability, high wear resistance, and for calcium phosphates, mainly for their compositional similarity with the mineral phase of bone. But the potential of any ceramic material to be used as an implant in vivo depends upon its ability to withstand complex stresses at the site of application and its compatibility with the biological environment. The superior biocompatibility of calcium phosphates contributed by their compositional resemblance with the bone mineral has allowed them to be used for copious applications inside the body. In 1920, Albee reported the first successful medical application of calcium phosphate bioceramics in humans, and in 1975 Nery et al. reported the first dental application of these ceramics in animals. In a very short span of time, bioceramics have come a long way and have found applications in numerous ways as in replacements of hips, knees, teeth, tendons and ligaments and repair for periodontal disease, maxillofacial reconstruction, augmentation and stabilization of the jawbone and in spinal fusion.

In all the spheres of past, present and prospected applications of bioceramics, calcium phosphates have a significant contribution. Today,

calcium phosphates are the materials of choice in both dentistry and medicine. They have been used in the field of biomedical engineering owing to the range of properties that they offer, from tricalcium phosphates being resorbable to hydroxyapatite being bioactive; they are undeniably the current rage for clinical usage. They exhibit considerably improved biological affinity and activity compared to other bioceramics such as alumina, zirconia, coralline, ALCAP (aluminum calcium phosphate ceramics), ZCAP (zinc calcium phosphate oxide ceramics), ZSCAP (zinc sulphate calcium phosphate ceramics) and FECAP (ferric calcium phosphate oxide ceramics). However, unlike alumina and zirconia, these ceramics are mechanically weak and exhibit poor crack growth resistance, which limit their uses to non-load bearing applications such as osteoconductive coatings on metallic prosthesis and as nano-powders in spinal fusion. Among different forms of calcium phosphates, particular attention has been placed to tricalcium phosphate ($\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, TCP) and hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, HAp) due to their outstanding biological responses to the physiological environment. The contemporary health care industry uses calcium phosphate ceramics in various applications, depending upon whether a resorbable or bioactive material is ideal. The recent trend in bioceramic research is focused on overcoming the limitations of calcium phosphates, precisely hydroxyapatite ceramics and in improving their biological properties via exploring the unique advantages of nanotechnology.

The trend is shifting towards nano technology to improve the biological responses of HAp because nano-HAp is a constituent of bone, which is a natural composite of nano-HAp

with collagen fibers. The main constituents of bone are collagen (20 wt.%), calcium phosphate (69 wt.%), and water (9 wt.%). Additionally, other organic materials, such as proteins, polysaccharides, and lipids are also present in small quantities. Collagen, which can be considered as the matrix, is in the form of small microfibrils. It is difficult to observe distinct collagen fibers because of its net-like mass appearance. The diameter of the collagen microfibrils varies from 100 to 2000 nm. Calcium phosphate in the form of crystallized hydroxyapatite (HAp) and/ or amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) provide stiffness to the bone. The HAp crystals, present in the form of plates or needles, are about 40–60 nm long, 20 nm wide, and 1.5–5 nm thick. They are deposited parallel to the collagen fibers, such that the larger dimension of crystals is along the long axis of the fiber. It is worth mentioning that the mineral phase present in the bone is not a discrete aggregation of the HAp crystals. It is rather made of a continuous phase, which is evidenced by a very good strength of the bone after a complete removal of the organic phase. The use of nano-HAp in orthopedics is therefore considered to be very promising, owing to its dimensional similarity with the bone crystals.

It has been established that nanotechnology offers a unique approach to overcome shortcomings of many conventional materials. From nanomedicine to nanofabrics, this promising technology has encompassed almost all disciplines of human life. Nanostructured materials offer much improved performances than their larger particle sized counterparts due to their large surface to volume ratio and unusual chemical/electronic synergistic effects. Nanoscale ceramics can exhibit significant ductility before failure contributed by the grain-boundary phase. In 1987, Karch et al. reported that, with nanograin size, a brittle ceramic could permit a large plastic strain up to 100%. Nanostructured biomaterials promote osteoblast adhesion and proliferation, osseointegration, and the deposition of

calcium containing minerals on the surface of these materials. Also, nanostructured ceramics can be sintered at a lower temperature thereby problems associated with high temperature sintering processes are also eliminated. It is possible to enhance both mechanical and biological performance of calcium phosphates by controlling characteristic features of powders such as particle size and shape, particle distribution and agglomeration. Nanoceramics clearly represent a promising class of orthopedic and dental implant formulations with improved biological and biomechanical properties. This paper will discuss the recent developments in the field of nanoscale calcium phosphate based bioceramics with a brief overview on classification, properties and applications of conventional forms.

1.1 Calcium phosphates

Calcium phosphates being light in weight, chemically stable and compositionally similar to the mineral phase of the bone are preferred as bone graft materials in hard tissue engineering. They are composed of ions commonly found in physiological environment, which make them highly biocompatible. In addition, these bioceramics are also resistant to microbial attack, pH changes and solvent conditions. They exist in different forms and phases depending on temperature, partial pressure of water and the presence of impurities. HAp, β -TCP, α -TCP, biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) [14], monocalcium phosphate monohydrate (MCPM) and unsintered apatite (AP) are different forms of commercially available calcium phosphates currently used in the biomedical industry. Table 1 summarizes the physical properties of various forms of calcium phosphates currently used in the biomedical industry. Different phases are used in different applications depending upon whether a resorbable or bioactive material is desired. HAp is the ideal phase for application inside human body because of its excellent stability above pH 4.3, human blood pH being 7.3. Table 2 presents solubility and pH stability of different forms of calcium phosphates in aqueous solution.

Table-1**Physical properties of various phases of calcium phosphate bioceramics**

Sl. No	Phases	Chemical formulae	Ca/P ratio	Crystal structure	Density (g/cm ³)
1.	α -Tricalcium phosphate (α -TCP)	Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	3/2	Monoclinic, P21/a space group, lattice constants: a = 12.887 Å, b = 27.280 Å, c = 15.219 Å; β = 126.20°	2.86
2.	β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP)	Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	3/2	Pure hexagonal, rhombohedral, space group R3cH, unit cell dimensions: a = b = 10.439 Å, c = 37.375 Å, and α = β = 90°, γ = 120°	3.07
3.	Tetracalcium phosphate (TTCP)	Ca ₄ P ₂ O ₉	2/1	Monoclinic, space group P21, a = 7.023, b = 11.986, c = 9.473; β = 90.90°	3.05

One of the major shortcomings of calcium phosphate bioceramics is their poor mechanical strength under complex stress states. Further, it has been proved that the bioactivity of synthetic calcium phosphates (micron size powder) is inferior to natural apatite, the bone mineral. Like other ceramic materials, the tensile and compressive strengths of

calcium phosphates are governed by the presence of voids, pores or interstices, which results during the process of densification while sintering. However, unlike most advanced ceramics, calcium phosphates are difficult to sinter and thus are mechanically weak. The resistance to fatigue is another essential factor for (tensile) load-bearing implants. In terms of Weibull factor, n, values of n = 50 to 100 usually signify good resistance but values of n = 10 to 20 are insufficient and may fail in several months of usage. For conventional HAp, n = 50 in dry environment and n = 12 in a wet physiological implant bed, which is below the satisfactory limit as reported by Putter et al. Nanotechnology is one of the approaches, which has been explored recently to improve both the strength and toughness of this novel group of bioceramics to make them useful in load-bearing applications.

Table-2**Solubility and pH stability of different phases of calcium phosphates**

Sl. No.	Phases	Solubility at 25 °C, $-\log(K_{sp})$	pH stability range in aqueous solution at 25 °C
1.	Hydroxyapatite (HAp)	116.8	9.5–12
2.	β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP)	28.9	Cannot be precipitated from aqueous solutions
3.	α -Tricalcium phosphate (α -TCP)	25.5	Cannot be precipitated from aqueous solutions
4.	Tetracalcium phosphate (TTCP)	38–44	Cannot be precipitated from aqueous solutions
5.	Dicalcium phosphate dihydrate (DCPD)	6.59	2.0–6.0

6.	Dicalcium phosphate anhydrate (DCPA)	6.90	Stable at temperatures above 100 °C
7.	Amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP)	Cannot be measured precisely. However, the following values were reported: 25.7 ± 0.1 (pH 7.40), 29.9 ± 0.1 (pH 6.00), 32.7 ± 0.1 (pH 5.28).	Always metastable. The composition of a precipitate depends on the solution pH value and composition.
8.	Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite (CDHA)	~85.1	6.5–9.5

Conventional calcium phosphate based ceramic powders suffer from poor sinterability possibly due to their low surface area (typical 2–5 m²/g). In addition, it has been also recorded that the resorption process of synthetic calcium phosphates (conventional forms) is quite different from that of bone mineral. Bone mineral crystals are in nano-size with a very large surface area. They are grown in an organic matrix and have very loose crystal-to-crystal bonds; therefore the resorption by osteoclasts is quite homogeneous. Calcium phosphates (micron size), on the contrary, present a low surface area and have strong crystal-to-crystal bond. Resorption takes place in two steps: (i) disintegration of particles and (ii) dissolution of the crystals. Nanoscale bioceramics is one of the emerging approaches that have been extensively studied recently by various researchers to find a solution to these long standing problems associated with calcium phosphates. In a recent publication, Kim et al. reported that biomineralization of calcium phosphate nanocrystals on ceramics with specific compositions and structures is a core mechanism of bioactivity, that inspires acellular and protein free biomimetic strategies for bio-interactive

materials with new physical, chemical and biological functions, e.g., bioactive surface functionalizations on tough metallic and ceramic materials, sol-gel derivation of bioactive ceramic-polymer nano-hybrids and textured biomimetic depositions of nano-calcium phosphate on polymer templates.

Crystallization of various salts of calcium phosphates like hydroxyapatite (HAp) and β -TCP depends on Ca/P ratio, presence of water and impurities, and temperature. For instance, in a wet environment and at a lower temperature (< 900 °C), the formation of hydroxyapatite is most likely to happen, but in a dry atmosphere and at a higher temperature, β -TCP is more likely to form.

2.1. Hydroxyapatite

Hydroxyapatite ((Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂), HAp) is a bioactive ceramics widely used as powders or in particulate forms in various bone repairs and as coatings for metallic prostheses to improve their biological properties. HAp is thermodynamically the most stable calcium phosphate ceramic compound at the pH, temperature and composition of the physiological fluid. Recently, HAp has been used for a variety of biomedical applications, including matrices for drug release control. Due to the chemical similarity between HA and mineralized bone of human tissue, synthetic HAp exhibits strong affinity to host hard tissues. Formation of chemical bond with the host tissue offers HAp a greater advantage in clinical applications over most other bone substitutes, such as allografts or metallic implants. Some of the present and proposed applications of nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite bioceramics are presented in Table 3.

HAp possesses a hexagonal structure with a P63/m space group and cell dimensions $a = b = 9.42 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 6.88 \text{ \AA}$, where P63/m refers to a space group with a six-fold symmetry axis with a three-fold helix and a microplane. It has an exact stoichiometric Ca/P ratio of 1.67 and is chemically very similar to the mineralized human bone. However, in spite of chemical similarities, mechanical performance of synthetic HAp is very poor compared to bone. In addition, the bone mineral present a higher bioactivity compared to synthetic HAp.

Table-3**Present and proposed applications of nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite and its composites**

Year	Present and proposed applications	Reference
2002	HAp/chitosan (CTS) nano-composites of homogeneous microstructure were formed.	[25]
	They were proposed to be helpful for producing uniform nanomaterials with best properties for biomedical applications.	
2004	Bioresorbable nano-HAp composite bone paste with natural polysaccharide and chitosan anticipated to act as a bioresorbable bone substitute with superior bioactivity and osteoconductivity <i>in vivo</i> .	[24]
2004	HAp/polyanhydride nano-composite was formed.	[28]
	If the HAp content in the polyanhydrides was appropriate and compositions in the crosslinking network are suitable, it meets the rehabilitation need of different fracture bones in human body, both in mechanical properties and in the biodegradable rate.	
2004	Nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite and calcium sulphate as biodegradable composite carrier material for local delivery of antibiotics in bone infections offers a new treatment option in osteomyelitis.	[26]
2004	Nano-HAp coatings on surfaces of titanium prosthesis to get improved	[27]

	biocompatibility and	
	mechanical performance of the prosthesis.	

Many researchers have observed that the mechanical strength and fracture toughness of HAp ceramics can be improved by the use of different sintering techniques which include addition of a low melting secondary phase to achieve liquid phase sintering for better densification, incorporation of sintering additives to enhance densification through grain boundary strengthening, and use of nanoscale ceramic powders for better densification contributed by large surface area to volume ratios of nano-size powders. It is believed that nanoscale HAp has the potential to revolutionize the field of biomedical science from bone regeneration to drug delivery. During the past 10 years, much attention has been given to nanostructured HAp calcium phosphate ceramic, with major research emphases of production of nanoscale powders to improve the mechanical as well as biological properties. Importance and advantages of nanocrystalline HAp were highlighted by Sarig and Kahana in a 2002 issue of the Journal Crystal Growth 237. In their work, Sarig and Kahana could synthesize HAp with 300 nm edges, which were loosely aggregated into spherulites of 2–4 μm dimensions. Nanocrystalline HAp powders exhibit improved sinterability and enhanced densification due to greater surface area, which could improve the fracture toughness as well as other mechanical properties. Moreover, nano-HAp is also expected to have better bioactivity than coarser crystals.

2.1.1. Synthesis of nano-hydroxyapatite powders

A number of powder processing techniques have been developed and used to synthesize calcium phosphate based ceramic powders, mainly HAp, which include sol–gel synthesis, solid state reactions, co-precipitation, hydrothermal reaction, microemulsion syntheses and mechanochemical synthesis. Table 4 presents the chronological development of synthesis of nano-HAp ceramics during the last 10 years. Recently, the use of sol–gel method for synthesis of calcium phosphates has gained interest because of its unique advantages. The sol–gel method offers a molecular-level mixing of the calcium and phosphorus precursors, which is capable

of improving chemical homogeneity and reducing synthesis temperature in comparison with conventional methods. Many variations of the sol-gel process have been developed and used to produce powders with different Ca/P ratios by altering the quantity and the composition of precursors and processing variables.

Liu et al. and Yingchao et al. synthesized nano-HAp of 8–10 nm sizes via template mediated and non-template mediated sol-gel techniques, respectively. In most literature on synthesis of HAp by sol-gel process, phosphorous alkoxide has been used as precursor for P. Liu et al. [21] used triethyl phosphate and calcium nitrate as the precursors respectively for P and Ca for HAp synthesis. Kuriakose et al. suggested that agars can also be used to synthesize HAp using similar precursors at low temperatures. These processes require high temperature operation and produces multi-phase powder. A relatively simpler sol-gel process using ethanol and/or water as solvent has also been reported to obtain stoichiometric, nanocrystalline single phase HAp. Suchanek et al. synthesized nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite powder by the citric acid sol-gel combustion method. The attractive features of this method were to synthesize materials with high purity, better homogeneity and high surface area in a single step. Varma et al. synthesized the nano-HAp by polymeric combustion method and self-propagating combustion synthesis using novel body fluid solutions.

Shih et al. synthesized nano-hydroxyapatite powder (Ca/ P = 1.67) of 20 nm particle size by the hydrolysis method. They also observed that the HAp particle size increases with the annealing temperature. An annealing temperature of 1000 °C resulted in an average increase in particle diameter to 50 nm after soaking for 4 h. Xu et al. used radio frequency (rf) plasma spray process to synthesize nano-sized HAp powder with particle size in the range of 10–100 nm.

Synthesis of stoichiometric nano-HAp powders by sol-gel method is relatively easy. It gives higher product purity, more homogeneous composition and comparatively low synthesis temperatures than other methods. Sol-gel derived

HAp is always accompanied by secondary phase of calcium oxide. Phosphorous, alkoxides, gels and ethanol can be used as solvents in this method. Kuriakose et al. synthesized nanocrystalline HAp of size 1.3 nm radius that is stable till 1200 °C without any by-products in the samples synthesized with pores in the crystal planes, using the later as solvent. Synthesis of pure HAp crystals of 8–10 nm size can also be done by a novel sol-gel technique using agars. Han et al. synthesized nanocrystalline HAp powder at low calcination temperature of 750 °C by citric acid sol-gel combustion method. The grain size of the resulting powder was found to be between 80 and 150 nm and the open porosity to be 19%. Sarig et al. synthesized nanocrystalline plate-shaped particles of HAp, directly precipitated from dilute calcium chloride and sodium phosphate solutions at ambient temperature. The solution was introduced to microwave irradiation immediately after mixing. The pH of the solution was kept 7.4 to make HAp suitable for medical applications. This method is a relatively fast method to synthesize nano-HAp.

In our research, we have synthesized nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, HAp) powders using ethanol-based and water-based sol-gel techniques, and compared them. Calcium nitrate and triethyl phosphite were used as precursors for calcium and phosphorous, respectively. In the ethanol-based method, triethyl phosphite sol was diluted in anhydrous ethanol with a small amount of distilled water. A stoichiometric amount of calcium nitrate, dissolved in anhydrous ethanol, was subsequently added dropwise into the hydrolyzed phosphite sol. As-formed gel was aged for 16 h, then dried, and calcined at 300–800 °C to produce nano-HAp. In the water-based method, phosphorous and calcium precursors were hydrolyzed in distilled water, separately, under vigorous stirring. Calcium nitrate sol was added dropwise into the hydrolyzed phosphite sol and then aged and dried. Calcination was carried out at 250–600 °C. Transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) was used to determine particle size of powders produced via both of these techniques. TEM analyses revealed that particle size diameter of powders synthesized via ethanol-based and water-based methods were 20–50 nm and 5–10 nm in diameter, respectively. Powder X-ray diffraction technique was used to analyze the phases. X-ray diffraction results showed that the apatite phase

first appeared at 400 °C and the HAp content increased with increase in calcination temperatures.

Nano-sized HAp particles can also be prepared by chemical precipitation through aqueous solutions of calcium chloride and ammonium hydrogen phosphate. Pang et al. observed that the crystallinity and crystallite size of HAp increases with the increase of synthetic temperature and ripening time when the solution is prepared by this method. Also, the morphology change of HAp nanoparticles is related to their crystallinity. Regular shape and smooth surface of the nanoparticles can be obtained by higher crystallinity of HAp. They observed needle-like shape of nanoparticles with rough surface and blurred contour and higher combined water content for lesser crystalline HAp whereas bar-like shape with smooth surface, clear contour and lower water content was observed for nanoparticles with higher crystallinity.

Mechanochemical processing (MCP) is another compelling method to produce nanostructured HAp in solid state. Yeong et al. used appropriate amounts of calcium hydrogen phosphate ($\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and calcium oxide (CaO). Yang et al. reported the nano-sized HAp powders nano-size using the MCP technique.

2.1.2. Nano - hydroxyapatite based composites in tissue engineering

HAp has been widely used for biomedical implants and bone regeneration applications. However, its applications in periodontal and alveolar ridge augmentation are limited due to its particle mobilization and slow resorbable nature. To overcome these limitations, HAp is widely used in combination with some polymers and other compounds as composites.

To augment its usage in this area, Murugan et al. prepared and characterized HA composite bone paste with a natural polysaccharide, chitosan, using wet chemical method at low temperature. Their findings suggest that the HA/chitosan composite paste would be highly beneficial for the particle immobilization upon implantation and may be a candidate bioresorbable material as bone substitute.

Chen et al. from Xiamen University, China, prepared and characterized nano-sized hydroxyapatite particles and hydroxy-apatite/chitosan nano-composite for use in biomedical materials. They were able to produce nano-HAp particles of 20–30 nm width and 50–60 nm length and particles of almost homogeneous microstructure so that they can be useful in producing uniform nanomaterials. The nanostructured HAp/chitosan composite promises to have excellent biomedical properties for use in the clinics.

Recently, in 2004, Rauschmann et al. assessed the material properties of a calcium sulphate nanoparticulate HAp composite material and analyzed its in vitro uptake and release of vancomycin (antibacterial used for treating infections in different parts of the body, usually given in combination with other antibiotics) and gentamicin (antibacterial used for treating infections of the skin) antibiotics. Their results suggest this composite to be a new treatment option in osteomyelitis (acute or chronic bone infection usually caused by bacteria) owing to its good biocompatibility and sufficient antibiotic release.

Zhang et al. of Tsinghua University (Beijing) described their use of conventional and high-resolution transmission electron spectroscopy (HRTEM) to study nanofibrils of mineralized collagen. They have found a key mechanism behind how these fibrils self-assemble. They have also demonstrated for the first time that HAp crystals associate specifically with the surfaces of collagen fibrils. They observed that the HAp crystals align themselves with the long axis of the collagen fibrils. Previously, other researchers had found that anions on the collagen molecules act as nucleation sites for HAp crystals and that the positions of the hydroxyl groups in HAp crystals lie along the same axis as the carbonyl groups in collagen.

2.2. Tricalcium phosphate

Tricalcium phosphate is thermodynamically stable only at elevated temperatures [1000–1500 °C]. It has been proved to be resorbable in vivo with new bone growth replacing the implanted TCP. β -TCP and α -TCP are the two forms of TCP that are known to exist. β -TCP transforms to α -TCP at around 1200 °C. The later phase is stable in the range of 700–1200 °C. α -TCP, however, has received very little interest

in the biomedical field. The disadvantage for using α -TCP is its quick resorption rate, which limits its usage in this area. On the other hand β -TCP, also known as β -whitlockite, is essentially a slowly degrading bioresorbable calcium phosphate ceramic (CPC) and is a promising material in the field of biomedical applications such as orthopedics. It has also been observed to have significant biological affinity and activity and responds very well to the physiological environments. Because of its slow degradation characteristic, the porous β -TCP is regarded as an ideal material for bone substitutes that should degrade by advancing bone growth. These factors give β -TCP an edge over other biomedical materials when it comes to resorbability and replacement of the implanted TCP in vivo by the new bone tissue. Its excellent biocompatibility makes it a possible material to act as a scaffold allowing bone regeneration and growth. X-ray patterns reveal that β -TCP has a pure hexagonal crystal structure. It is reported that the resorbability of β -TCP in vivo might be strongly related to the characterization and stability of the β -TCP structure.

A number of synthesis methods have been used to produce β -TCP powders. The conventional methods include solid-state process and wet-chemical method. The wet-chemical method gives Ca-deficient apatite ($\text{Ca}_9(\text{HPO}_4)(\text{PO}_4)_5(\text{OH})$, CDHA) with the same molar ratio of Ca/P as that of TCP. It needs to be calcined above 700–800 °C to transform into β -TCP as shown by the following reaction:

Synthesis of nano- β -TCP has been formulated by many researchers using starting materials as $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Ca}\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the Ca sources and H_3PO_4 as the P sources. Bow et al. synthesized nano-sized β -TCP powder of ~50 nm particle diameter at room temperature in methanol solvent. They found that phase transformation was taking place from CaHPO_4 , intermediate amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) phases (including ACP1 and ACP2 with different structures) to final β -TCP with increase in aging time. They observed that the incorporation of carbonate helps in suppressing the transformation of ACP1 phase with HAp-like structure into poorly crystalline CDHA and favors the formation of β -TCP phase. It was observed that the presence of micropores in the sintered material affect the bioresorption of TCP-based ceramic implants, therefore, the size and amount of macro-and microporosity must be controlled closely during manu-facturing processes. SEM studies

revealed that the appearance of needles or petal-like plates is characteristic of nano- β -TCP-based calcium phosphate cements. The nano-TCP powders can be compacted into cylindrical pallets and then sintered for mechanical and biodegradation studies to achieve appropriate mechanical strength to be used as drug delivery devices. Metsger et al. reported a 21 GPa value for the Young's modulus of nano- β -TCP ceramic. The mechanical strength of the cement was enhanced when the nanostructures were immersed for 24 h and 7 days in SBF.

Nano- β -tricalcium phosphate cements can serve as drug delivery systems for a variety of remedies such as antibiotics, anti-tumor and anti-inflammatory drugs, etc., that can easily be added to them. Also, β -TCP prepared by wet precipitation procedure from an aqueous solution of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and NaH_2PO_4 and calcined at 1150 °C can be used as bone substitutes after grinding and sieving to obtain the desired particle size. A subsidiary of Tredegar Corporation has recently received FDA clearance to market a new resorbable β -tricalcium phosphate bone void filler device used to treat osseous defects of the skeletal system. Future directions are aimed at creating a therapeutic nano-TCP coating that has a dual beneficial effect: osteoconductive properties combined with the ability to deliver therapeutic agents, proteins, and growth factors directly into the coating. These new coatings may offer the ability to stimulate bone growth, combat infection, and, ultimately, increase implant lifetime.

2.3. Tetracalcium phosphate

Tetracalcium phosphate ($(\text{Ca}_4(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{O})$, TTCP) is the most basic calcium orthophosphate ceramic. However, its solubility in water is higher than that of HAp. TTCP cannot be precipitated from aqueous solutions, and thus can only be prepared by a solid-state reaction above 1300 °C. TTCP is not very stable in aqueous solutions, it slowly hydrolyzes to HA and calcium hydroxide. Consequently, TTCP is never found in biological calcifications. In medicine, TTCP is widely used for the preparation of various self-setting cements. However, not much has been reported for the synthesis and applications of nano-TTCP.

3. Conclusion

Nanophase calcium phosphate bioceramics have gained regard in the biomedical field due to their superior biological and biomechanical properties. HAP and β -TCP are essentially the main calcium phosphates used in the clinics at present. Several ways of synthesis of both these forms of CPCs on the nanoscale have evolved in the past few decades. Due to the chemical similarity between HAP and mineralized bone of human tissue, synthetic HAP exhibits strong affinity to host hard tissues. Nano-HAP is used primarily as bioactive coatings on metallic prosthesis of bioinert materials like titanium and its alloys, in bone tissue repairs and implants and also for drug delivery. Nanoscale β -TCP exhibits significant biological affinity and activity and responds very well to the physiological environments. Also owing to its slow degradation characteristic, the porous β -TCP is regarded as an ideal material for bone substitutes that should degrade by advancing bone growth. It also finds applications in drug delivery systems and as bone substitutes. A lot of research in this area is expected in the nano-zone for much enhanced applications in drug delivery systems and as resorbable scaffolds that can be replaced by the endogenous hard tissues with the passage of time.

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